

PREDICTION OF FRACTURE INITIATION IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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The need for experimental data on the fracture behavior of fiber-reinforced composites under complex loading has been recognized for some time. Recent publications have pointed out that the need still exists. In 1975, Rowlands stated that "Most available strength information is based on uniaxial stress states, while practical applications invariably involve at least biaxial loading." More recently, Morris and Hahn pointed out that "A review of the literature indicates that most of the work in fracture of composites has emphasized Mode I* loading. By comparison, mixed-mode fracture has received little attention. Most of the available mixed-mode data falls in the category of unidirectional composites, with the crack being parallel to the fiber." Guess and Gerstle state much the same: "A survey of the literature for experimental data on composites revealed that most data are from uniaxial stress tests. However, the loading on composite structures will be, in general, more complex than uniaxial stress states." The reason, of course, for the scarcity of complex loading data is that it is much more difficult and more expensive to obtain. Numerous analytical criteria have been examined with regard to their ability to predict the strength behavior of composites under complex loading in order to extend the limited data available. Unfortunately, these attempts have met with only limited success. For all practical purposes, we are dependent on experimental data to define the strength behavior of composites under complex loading.

A program was initiated at the Naval Research Laboratory to characterize the fracture behavior of composite materials. As a result of experiences in the early stages of this study, several criteria were established. First, fracture mechanics concepts would be utilized, in that attention would be focused on defining the conditions under which fracture initiates from a controlled defect or stress concentrator. However, the study would not be limited to using existing fracture mechanics parameters such as strain energy release rate G , stress intensity factor K , or the J -integral, established for isotropic materials. Second, experimental studies should be conducted under general in-plane loading, to simulate service conditions as closely as practical. Third, with the very large number of variables involved in composite materials, tests should be relatively inexpensive to conduct. This means that the specimens should be of simple geometry to reduce machining costs and be small to reduce materials costs, and that the time to conduct a test should be relatively short. However the specimen dimensions should be large enough relative to fiber diameter or lamina thickness so that the material could be considered

homogeneous and orthotropic for purposes of analysis. Fourth, analytic expressions should be developed to permit interpolation and extrapolation of data. Fifth, the data obtained should be usable by design engineers. Finally, laboratory tests should be conducted on structural prototypes to demonstrate that the predictions based on the laboratory coupons are indeed valid.

The program involved three parts: (1) the development of a suitable loading system for applying complex loading; (2) the development of failure criteria from fracture studies conducted under complex loading; (3) the demonstration of the validity of these failure criteria in laboratory studies on structural components.

*Mode I loading refers to cleavage or opening mode.